

content was estimated at 10, 12, 16, 20, 24, and 35 DAS.

Leaf chlorophyll content decreased with increasing age of seedlings (see table). Chlorophyll content in submerged seedlings was similar to that in nonsubmerged seedlings up to 6 d after submersion, then dropped drastically. After submersion ended, chlorophyll content continued to decrease for 4 d before recovery started.

B-9c-Md-3-3 had the highest chlorophyll content after submergence.

Chlorophyll content of leaves of submerged and nonsubmerged rice seedlings. West Bengal, India.

Variety	Chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt) of seedlings at given days after seeding										
	Nonsubmerged						Submerged			Recovery	
	10	12	16	20	24	35	12	16	20	24	35
B-9c-Md-3-3	2.16	2.14	1.92	1.87	1.84	1.73	2.84	1.43	1.58	0.46	2.27
CN540	5.12	1.73	2.64	1.98	2.13	2.13	2.68	1.92	0.46	0.77	–
CR126-42-1	3.50	2.55	1.95	1.73	1.56	1.43	3.80	1.54	1.30	0.62	–
FR13A	2.91	3.01	1.20	1.22	1.70	1.70	2.65	1.92	0.73	0.17	2.39
Mohon	3.21	3.73	2.37	2.19	1.67	0.94	5.03	2.10	0.64	0.57	–
OC1393	4.32	3.88	2.86	2.16	2.04	1.70	4.28	1.81	0.71	1.10	2.27
Mean	3.54	2.84	2.06	1.86	1.82	1.61	3.55	1.79	0.91	0.62	2.31

CN540 seedlings had the highest chlorophyll content at 10 DAS, but

content decreased faster with aging. Three varieties died. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GRAIN QUALITY

Grain quality of new varieties PR 108 and PR 109 in Punjab, India

S.K. Uppal and G.S. Sidhu, Punjab Agricultural University, Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, India

Two new rice varieties were released in Punjab in 1986. PR108 is resistant to sheath blight and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), PR109 is resistant to bacterial blight and

WBPH. PR108 and PR109 are as high yielding as PR103 and PR106 and Jaya under disease- and insect-free conditions (see table).

Total rice recovery and head rice recovery of PR108 and PR109 equaled those of PR103, PR106, and PR4141 and head rice recovery was higher than Jaya's.

The new varieties have long, slender white grains. PR108 has high and PR 109 has intermediate amylose

content. Cooking quality compares favorably with that of PR106, PR4141, PR103, and Jaya. PR108 and PR109 have slightly higher protein content than other varieties.

With their good milling quality, desirable appearance, good cooking and eating quality, and good protein value, the new varieties are likely to be as acceptable to consumers and millers as PR106, which commands a premium price. □

Grain quality characteristics of rice varieties.^a Kapurthala, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Total rice recovery (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)		Length: breadth ratio	Cooking time (min)	Kernel elongation ratio	Volume expansion ratio	Amylose (%/dry basis)	Protein (%) at 14% moisture
				Paddy	Milled rice						
PR108	7.1	74.0	63.1	23.3	17.3	3.2	19	1.8	4.2	26.2	8.0
PR109	6.9	73.0	63.0	24.5	18.8	3.2	26	1.7	4.8	24.7	8.7
PR103	6.6	73.3	63.3	25.0	18.9	3.0	19	1.6	3.7	16.0	7.9
PR106	6.5	73.5	63.2	22.8	16.9	3.3	18	1.8	3.9	25.4	7.8
Jaya	7.1	75.2	56.6	27.3	21.6	2.5	22	1.7	4.2	26.3	7.8
PR4141	5.8	74.2	61.3	21.9	16.5	3.0	23	1.7	4.6	23.1	7.9

^aAv of 3 replications.

Relationship of agroclimatic parameters to high density grain production

S. P. Rao, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, A. P., India

Production of high density (HD) grains differs with crop duration, season, and N levels. We found that HD grain index (% of fully filled grain at 1.18 specific gravity divided by spikelets per panicle) is influenced

positively by crop duration and season and negatively by N level.

Long-duration varieties IET5656, Mahsuri, CR 1009, and Pankaj had higher HD grain indexes than the short- and medium-duration varieties